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EXPERIENCES OF STUDYING OIKONYMS IN SOCIO-ECONOMIC GEOGRAPHY OF UZBEKISTAN

Annotation. In this article, the study of geographical names in the Republic of Uzbekistan from an economic and social geographical point of view was studied. An analysis of the research work of local geographers is given.

Keywords: toponym, oikonym, geographical term, hydrooikonyms, orooikonyms, phytooikonyms and zoooikonyms, anthropooikonyms, ethnooikonyms, toponymic heritage.

Introduction. Geographical names have attracted the attention of scientists from various fields since ancient times. The issues of toponymy have been covered since ancient times in the literature of history, geography, and linguistics. Any science appears and develops under the influence of practical requirements. Toponymy first arose based on the practical needs of geography. The first travelers gave names to the lands they discovered, made the names of distant lands and cities known to everyone. Geographers were also those who collected geographical names [15]. Scientific study of the origin and history of geographic names, in particular, oikonyms, and their classification began relatively recently. For example, in the scientific research works of V.P.Semyonov-Tyan-Shansky, E.M.Murzaev, V.A.Zhuchkevich, H.L.Khanmagomedov, V.N.Kalutskov, L.S.Tsidipova many works have been carried out on theoretical issues, socio-economic geographical aspects and their classification [14]. In 2020, the Russian Geographical Society compiled and published a thematic atlas [8] consisting of special toponymic maps of the stability and change of the names of capitals, regions and district centers in the countries of the former Soviet Union in the last 100 years, that is, in the 20th and 21st centuries. In this atlas, in particular, information is given about some variable oikonyms in the territory of Uzbekistan.

Main part. The scientific study of geographical names, in particular the oikonyms, on the basis of their origin and history, their classification began in recent times. H.H.Hasanov, the scientist who started the geographical research of toponyms, in particular, oikonyms, in Uzbekistan. In his works, the scientist

attached great importance to scientific-theoretical aspects of toponymy, etymology, correct spelling and transcription of geographical names and terms, research of writing forms in national and other languages [12-13]. For example, we can find the following opinion about the Muynak oikonym: “Muynak” is a peninsula, a city in the south of the Aral Sea. This name is formed from the words muyin – “neck”, aq, in fact – “aq small”, which means “small neck”, “neck”, “peninsula” [13].

Toponymist scientist S.K.Karaev made a special contribution to the systematic research of the names of Uzbekistan [3, 9-10]. In his doctoral dissertation, the scientist for the first time comprehensively researched the formation and development of oikonyms in Uzbekistan. In particular, the historical-geographical roots of the composition of the oikonyms of Uzbekistan are deeply analyzed., maps of oikonyms of Uzbekistan consisting of natural-geographic and socio-economic geographic components have been created, detailed information is provided on local geographical terms and their role in the creation of oikonyms. S.K.Karaev noted that toponymy can greatly help historical geography in determining the geography of ancient types of economic activity, the names of ancient professions, ancient trade routes, and the geography of deposits of underground resources used in the past [3]. It should be recognized that S.K.Karaev was the first to create a map of production-related concepts in Uzbekistan. S.K.Karaev divided the oikonim into two groups:

1. Symbols denoting natural geographical objects.
2. Socio-economic oikonyms.

1. Symbols denoting natural geographic objects are derived from the names of water bodies, geomorphological conditions of places, flora and fauna, and other natural objects. They are divided into the following types: a) hydrooikonyms; b) orooikonyms; v) phytooikonyms; g) zoooikonyms.

2. Socio-economic oikonyms – oikonyms related to the economic activity of the population and are divided into the following types: a) anthropooikonyms; b) ethnooikonyms; v) oikonyms that are named according to the types of professions; g) trade-transport oikonyms; d) social oikonyms.

In places where the social structure of the population has been preserved, there are the following oikonyms: a) oikonyms formed according to the standard of living; b) oikonyms formed according to social origin; v) ideological names; g) oikonyms caused by the migration of the population.

Also, in his doctoral thesis, S.K.Karaev emphasizes that it is effective to use terms denoting their different categories to study the history of the emergence of settlements and their original functions, and describes many local geographical terms. At the same time, S.K.Karaev stated that the etymology of toponyms in our country cannot be determined without knowing the ethnonyms of the peoples of Central Asia, that it is necessary to look for the semantics of many toponyms, especially oikonyms, not in explanatory dictionaries but in ethnonymic and ethnographic lexicons.

K.M.Hakimov also made great contributions to the socio-economic geographical study of toponyms of Uzbekistan. In his candidate's thesis defended in 2010, he studied the importance of economic and socio-geographical characteristics of the region in the formation of place names, using the example of oikonoms of Jizzakh region [11]. In particular, it reflects the relationship between nature and society in place names, naming laws of settlements, semantic classification of regional toponymy, linguo-geographical analysis of regional place names and their mapping, the role of geographical terms in regional place names, the reflection of ethnonyms in the names of settlements, regional place names and their regulation problems, scientific recommendations on the naming of newly established settlements in the region have been developed.

The scientist writes about the names of settlements as follows: “Considering that settlements are a socio-economic category, their names can be considered in a certain sense more important than the names of natural-geographical objects, because the country of political, economic and social life is reflected in them”.

K.M.Hakimov emphasized that the natural conditions, economic and social indicators of the region, ethnography, geographical terms, and the ethnic composition of the population influenced the formation of the names of Jizzakh region and pointed out that as a characteristic of the names of the settlements. As a result of the scientist's research, in the process of studying the toponymy of the region, about 500 oikonoms were analyzed, and based on the above classification, a map of the first oikonoms of Jizzakh region was created.

K.M.Hakimov researches the oikonoms of Jizzakh region as oikonoms formed under the influence of natural and economic-social factors.

A) natural or natural geographical features. They, in turn, are divided into the following types: hydrooikonoms, oroikonoms, phytooikonoms and zoooikonoms.

B) socio-economic geographical oikonoms. They, in turn, are divided into the following types: anthropooikonoms, ethnooikonoms, oikonoms that reflect economic activity and neoikononym.

M.T.Mirakmalov is a geographer who has been contributing to the research of geographical terms and toponyms in our country. Although the scientist mainly deals with the natural-geographical aspects of toponymy and geographical terminology, some scientific works devoted to oikonomics have also been published. In particular, in this regard, his article entitled “Classification of oikonoms the Uzbekistan” is noteworthy [4]. In this article, based on the classifications of the oikonoms of M.T.Mirakmalov, E.M.Murzaev and S.K.Karaev, the oikonoms of of Uzbekistan are scientifically analyzed. The scientist's scientific article entitled “Specific features of toponymic research in small areas” [5] mainly talks about research methods of toponymy and presents many methods of researching oikonoms: the method of uppercase and lowercase signs of oikonoms (geometric and letter symbols), the same type, the same

language toponyms that appear with the help of related or identical toponymic terms areal method, repetition of certain toponymic events belonging to a place, method of diagrams, toponymic events in large areas qualitative and quantitative color methods, distribution of geographical names in specific areas, method of points, specific types of names in a region (for example, regions or districts of Uzbekistan) by the cartogram and cartogram method, the movement of geographical names by the method of moving lines.

Economic geographer Yu.I.Ahmadaliev contributed to the study of toponyms of Uzbekistan to a certain extent. Several works of the scientist on toponymy have been published, they are mainly devoted to the toponyms of the Ferghana Valley [1]. In the scientist's work "Toponyms of the Fergana region", he states that the oikonoms can be divided into two main groups:

1. Natural or natural geographical oikonoms;
2. Economic-social oikonoms.

Natural geographic oikonoms, in turn, are divided into names related to water, reflecting relief, flora and fauna, and economic-social oikonoms are divided into names of people, clans and tribes, production and social spheres. These, in turn, are divided into subgroups. In the work "Naming features of the oikonoms of Fergana region" co-authored with N.Okhunov, the scientific and theoretical basis of oikonym research, features and types of oikonoms are considered, as well as a brief explanatory dictionary of oikonoms of the region [7].

The socio-economic geographical aspects of oikonoms are also reflected in several scientific works of P.S.Otakulov, an expert who researched the toponyms of the Ferghana Valley [6]. In the works of the scientist, it is mentioned that in Ferghana region, the names of places related to handicrafts are given to more neighborhoods and streets, and at the same time, trade is of high importance in the economic life of people in Ferghana region.

O.O. Baltabaev for the first time analyzed a total of 1151 oikonym in the Republic of Karakalpakstan from a socio-geographic point of view [2]. The directions (spectral-stratigraphic, lexical-semantic, word formation, chronological, integral (territorial)) of the composition (structure) of regional oikonymic systems and the complex of social-geographical factors affecting them is theoretically based; the spectral-stratigraphic (linguistic), lexical-semantic (meaningful) and word-formation (topoterminological) composition of the oikonoms of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its administrative-territorial units (a total of 1151 place names) has been quantitatively analyzed, territorial differences in this regard and their social-geographical factors that influenced them are identified; for the first time, a two-level (2 regions and 7 sub-regions) oikonymic zoning scheme of the republic was developed based on a comprehensive analysis of the internal differences in the language, lexical-semantic and topoterminological structure of the oikonoms of Karakalpakstan; based on the period of formation, the oikonoms of Karakalpakstan were divided

into 3 chronological layers (before the Soviet period (including restored during the years of Independence), formed during the Soviet period and during the years of Independence), and on this basis, the historical stability of the oikonyms of the republic and its districts was evaluated; the essence of the concept of “toponymic heritage” and the criteria for determining its elements (a total of 9 criteria related to the historicity, symbolism and historical-cultural value of place names) have been developed, and on this basis, the registry of oikonyms recommended for recognition as objects of the toponymic heritage of the Republic of Karakalpakstan has been formed.

Conclusion. In general, some experience has been accumulated in the systematic study of oikonyms in the field of socio-economic geography in Uzbekistan and abroad, this experience, of course, serves as a scientific-methodical ground for current and subsequent scientific research in the relevant direction.

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